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ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence (AI), which is increasingly encountered and used in daily life, has led to revolutionary developments across various fields, especially with data processing and machine learning technologies. In the field of healthcare, AI makes significant contributions to healthcare professionals in various aspects such as screening, diagnosis and individualised treatment. In many areas such as interpretation of radiological images, classification of skin lesions, diabetic retinopathy screening, AI-supported systems have achieved similar accuracy rates with specialists. The integration of these technologies into primary healthcare improves diagnostic accuracy and enhances the efficiency and timeliness of patient management.

KEYWORDS

Artificial intelligence, diagnostic imaging, digital technology, family practice, primary health care

INTRODUCTION

The concept of artificial intelligence (AI) was first mentioned in the 1950s by John McCarthy as ‘the science and engineering of making intelligent machines’ (Reddy, Fox, & Purohit, 2019). According to the definition made by the European Commission, AI refers to systems that are designed by humans, perceive, analyse, interpret the environment, determine the best action based on this information and exhibit intelligent behaviours, and take actions with a certain degree of autonomy to achieve specific complex goals (European Commission, 2025).

Nowadays, it is possible to evaluate complex health data obtained from large data sources and to make predictions based on these data with AI. These developments provide significant contributions to healthcare professionals, especially in diagnostic processes, early detection of diseases, screening and follow-up, and individualised treatment approaches. These technologies, which are considered as a part of digital transformation in the field of healthcare, are widely used in many fields of practice from clinical decision support systems to the analysis of medical images (Reddy, Fox, & Purohit, 2019).

METHODS

In recent years, AI technologies have been widely used in the interpretation of radiological images by both radiology specialists and non-radiologist clinicians. As a result of a meta-analysis aiming to compare AI and healthcare professionals in the interpretation of radiological images, the sensitivity of deep learning models in diagnosis was 87% and specificity 92.5%, while the sensitivity of healthcare professionals was 86.4% and specificity 90.5% (Liu et al., 2019).

Imaging technologies are one of the areas where AI is used most frequently in a wide range from magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) to ultrasonography (USG), from computerised tomography (CT) to mammography. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has approved more than 200 commercial radiological AI products. They offer benefits such as detection of suspicious positive findings such as intracranial haemorrhage, pneumothorax, detection and classification of lesions such as pulmonary nodules and breast abnormalities, image reconstruction. These systems are also capable of detecting tissue densities and predicting future adverse events. The usage of alternative options instead of invasive diagnostic methods has increased with AI. The use of advanced AI models by family doctors in their clinical practice may reduce the complexity of technical interpretation. A study has shown that residents using AI in pulmonary X-ray interpretation have similar performance compared to specialist radiologists. Especially in rural areas where consultation to

radiologists is restricted, AI will empower the family doctors. Portable and cost-effective imaging techniques are also often supported by AI. Portable ultrasound probes, paired with AI-enabled smartphone applications, provide accessibility and manoeuvrability to family doctors in the use of ultrasound in echocardiography or obstetric care (Rajpurkar & Lungren, 2023).

RESULTS

On the other hand, early diagnosis of cancers in radiological images and pathologies with the help of machine learning and deep learning algorithms has recently been on the agenda. These technologies have been reported to have comparable performance with specialists (Gaur & Jagtap, 2022). AI can be used in the detection of malignant lesions from skin photographs, interpretation of mammography images, pathological evaluation of tissue samples, and analysis of colonoscopy videos to identify polyps with high accuracy. Further investigations should be carried out to improve the quality assessment, sensitivity and specificity of these systems. Today, there is a potential for overdiagnosis with these technologies (Elemento, Leslie, Lundin, & Tourassi, 2021).

In a study conducted in 2023, there were significant increases in cancer detection rate, recall rate and positive predictive value with AI assistance that automatically detected and emphasised lesions suspicious for breast cancer (Eliás-Cabot et al., 2024). With the use of AI in mammography examination, breast cancer risk estimation is performed, lesions are identified and classified, and responses to treatment are predicted. With faster and more accurate interpretation, the quality of healthcare services is improved, workload is reduced and unnecessary biopsies are prevented (Subasi & Özçelik, 2023).

The primary healthcare settings have many patients applying with dermatological complaints. It is very critical for family doctors to recognise suspicious skin lesions at an early stage by performing appropriate diagnostic triage for these patients. According to a systematic review conducted on AI algorithms for early diagnosis of skin cancers in primary health care, AI-supported systems provided diagnostic accuracy of 89.5% in melanoma, 85.3% in squamous cell carcinoma, 87.6% in basal cell carcinoma and 88.8% in the discrimination of benign-malignant lesions. AI supported systems require training according to different skin types and colours. At the same time, the specificity of these systems should be increased to avoid overdiagnosis and unnecessary biopsies (Jones et al., 2022). According to a systematic review published in 2024, there are performance differences between these devices. Larger and more diverse datasets tend to produce more robust and generalisable results when combined with high-quality images and reliable data sets (Furriel et al., 2024). Diabetes mellitus is a chronic disease that requires long-term follow-up due to its microvascular and macrovascular complications. Globally, diabetic retinopathy is the most common cause of vision loss. As the first point of contact for these patients, family doctors play an important role in the early diagnosis and prevention of diabetic retinopathy. Diabetic retinopathy screening is performed every one to two years in diabetic patients and family doctors periodically refer their patients to the secondary or tertiary healthcare centre (Alnahdi et al., 2023). Nowadays, AI-supported cameras are developed to screen for retinopathy in primary care without the need for fundus dilatation. In a study comparing ophthalmologists, retina specialists and AI in terms of detecting more than mild diabetic retinopathy (mtmDR), the sensitivity of retina specialists was 59.5% and specificity was 98.9%, while the sensitivity of the AI system was 97% and specificity was 88%. In general ophthalmologists, the sensitivity was 20.6% and specificity was 99.8%, while the sensitivity of AI was 96.5% and specificity was 86% (Lim et al., 2022).

In a research assessing the diagnostic classification of ocular diseases including diabetic retinopathy and glaucoma, the prognosis of ocular diseases such as the risk of neovascular age-related macular degeneration (AMD) in the contralateral eye over a 1-year period, and the 3-year prediction of cardiovascular and neurodegenerative diseases from these images, it was found that an AI-supported system analysing retinal images performed reasonably well (Zhou et al., 2023).

DISCUSSION

There are many AI-supported systems that can be used for diagnosis in primary healthcare and physicians can make faster and more accurate diagnoses with these systems. With the integration of digital technologies into the health systems of countries and the development of AI algorithms, it is expected that the effect of AI on medical diagnosis will increase even more in the future (Umaphy et al., 2023).

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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